

CYTOTOXIC AND GENOTOXIC EVALUATION OF *ARTOCARPUS HETEROPHYLLUS*
STEM BARK EXTRACT USING THE *ALLIUM CEPA* ASSAYEtti Imaobong Christopher^{1*}, Nsiong Abasi Xavier¹, Uduak Anthony Inwang², Ochoi Godswill Sunday¹, Imoh Imeh Johnny³¹Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria.²Department of Physiology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu Alike, Ikwo, Nigeria.³Department of Pharmacognosy and Natural Medicine, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

The increasing reliance on medicinal plants has raised concerns about their safety, particularly with long-term use. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (jackfruit) is widely recognized for its antidiabetic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties; however, limited data exist on the toxicological risks associated with its stem bark, which is often used in traditional medicine. This study evaluated the cytotoxic and genotoxic potential of *A. heterophyllus* stem bark extract using the *Allium cepa* assay. Root growth inhibition, mitotic index, and chromosomal aberrations were measured following exposure to different extract concentrations. Results showed a concentration-dependent inhibition of root growth and a reduction in mitotic index, accompanied by observable chromosomal abnormalities. These findings suggest that while *A. heterophyllus* stem bark possesses medicinal value, it may also pose cytogenotoxic risks at certain concentrations. The *Allium cepa* assay provided an efficient and cost-effective screening method, underscoring the need for further *in vivo* toxicological studies to ensure the safe use of this plant in therapeutic formulations.

KEYWORDS: *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, stem bark, cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, *Allium cepa* assay, chromosomal aberrations.

INTRODUCTION

The global use of medicinal plants has expanded considerably, with the World Health Organization estimating that nearly 80% of the world's population relies on herbal remedies for primary healthcare.^[1,2] These plants are rich in phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, and saponins, which confer therapeutic benefits ranging from antimicrobial and antioxidant to antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory activities.^[3,4] Despite these benefits, concerns remain about the safety and potential cytogenotoxic effects of prolonged or unregulated use, as many bioactive compounds can exert dual beneficial and harmful effects depending on concentration and exposure.^[5,7]

Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam., commonly known as jackfruit, is a member of the Moraceae family and is native to South and Southeast Asia. Various parts of the plant—including fruits, leaves, roots, and stem bark—are used in folk medicine. Documented uses include antidiabetic, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities^[3,6,7] However, scientific evaluation

of its toxicological profile, particularly the stem bark, remains scarce. Given its ethnomedicinal application, it is critical to establish a safety baseline for its use.

The *Allium cepa* assay, first introduced by Levan (1938).^[8] is an established bioassay for assessing cytotoxicity and genotoxicity. It evaluates root growth inhibition, mitotic index, and chromosomal aberrations, providing results that correlate with mammalian systems.^[8,9] Its low cost, simplicity, and reliability make it widely applicable in toxicological screening of plant extracts, pollutants, and environmental contaminants.

This study aims to evaluate the cytotoxic and genotoxic effects of *A. heterophyllus* stem bark extract using the *Allium cepa* assay. Findings from this work are expected to fill existing gaps in the toxicological profiling of the plant, ensuring its safer integration into pharmacological use and guiding future drug development from natural sources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material Collection and Preparation

Fresh stem bark of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (jackfruit) was collected from Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The plant was identified and authenticated at the Department of Botany, University of Uyo, and a voucher specimen was deposited for future reference. The collected bark was washed with tap water, shade-dried at ambient temperature, and pulverized into fine powder using a mechanical grinder.

Preparation of Methanolic Extract

Thirty-two grams of powdered stem bark was macerated in 7.5 L of 80% methanol for 72 h with intermittent stirring. The mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the filtrate was concentrated using a water bath at 49°C. A dry extract yield of 29 g was obtained and stored at 4°C until required for bioassays. The percentage yield was calculated relative to the initial plant material.

Test Organism (*Allium cepa*)

Commercial onion bulbs (*Allium cepa* L.) of uniform size were procured from a local market in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The bulbs were air-dried for two weeks before use. The outer dry scales were carefully removed without damaging the root primordial to allow uniform root sprouting.

Experimental Design and Treatment Groups

The cytotoxic and genotoxic effects of *A. heterophyllus* stem bark extract were assessed using the *Allium cepa*

assay. Bulbs were divided into five groups (n = 5 per group)

- Group I: Negative control (distilled water)
- Group II: Positive control (methotrexate, 0.1 mg/mL)
- Group III: Extract at 25 mg/mL
- Group IV: Extract at 50 mg/mL
- Group V: Extract at 75 mg/mL

Bulbs were placed in beakers containing the test solutions and allowed to grow at room temperature for 72 h.

Root Growth Inhibition Assay

At the end of the exposure period, root lengths were measured in centimeters. Mean root lengths were compared across groups, and percentage inhibition was calculated relative to the negative control. The effective concentration required to inhibit 50% of root growth (EC₅₀) was determined using root growth inhibition curves.

Mitotic Index Determination

Root tips (1–2 cm) were excised from each bulb and fixed in freshly prepared ethanol:acetic acid (3:1, v/v) solution for 24 h. The fixed samples were hydrolyzed in 1N HCl at 60°C for 5 min and stained with 2% acetocarmine. Squash preparations were made and examined under a light microscope at ×1000 magnification. A total of 500 cells per slide were scored, and the mitotic index (MI) was calculated as:

$$MI = \frac{\text{Total number of cells observed}}{\text{Number of dividing cells}} \times 100 \text{ --- (1)}$$

Chromosomal Aberration Analysis

Cells from treated and control groups were observed for structural chromosomal abnormalities, including stickiness, laggards, bridges, vagrants, and c-mitosis. Aberrations were recorded as percentages of total dividing cells. Representative micrographs were taken for documentation.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 5). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey–Kramer multiple comparison post hoc test (GraphPad Prism, San

Diego, CA, USA). Statistical significance was accepted at p ≤ 0.05.

Root Growth Inhibition

Exposure of *Allium cepa* roots to aqueous stem bark extract of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* significantly inhibited root elongation in a concentration-dependent manner. After 72 hours, mean root length decreased from 2.96 ± 0.78 cm in the control group to 0.38 ± 0.06 cm at the highest tested concentration (75 mg/mL) (Figure. 1). The extract exhibited an IC₅₀ value of 28 mg/mL, indicating marked cytotoxicity (Figure. 2).

Fig 1: Root length of *Artocarpus heterophyllus*-treated *Allium cepa*. Data are presented as mean \pm S.E.M. Significant differences at *P < 0.05.

Figure 2: Growth inhibition of *Allium cepa* roots exposed to Aqueous stem bark extract of *Artocarpus heterophyllus*. IC₅₀ indicates concentration of AH that inhibited 50% of the *Allium cepa* root growth.

Effect on Root Number

Treatment also reduced the number of emerging roots per bulb. The control group produced 21.25 ± 1.54 roots, while methotrexate (0.1 mg/mL, positive control) limited

root emergence to 2.10 ± 0.02 roots. The extract progressively decreased root number from 13.25 ± 3.74 (25 mg/mL) to 6.66 ± 1.70 (75 mg/mL) (Table 1).

Table 1: Cytotoxicity of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* stem bark extract on growing roots of Onion (*Allium cepa*).

Treatment group	Concentration of extract (mg/mL)	Average root Number
Negative control	Tap water	21.25 ± 1.54
Methotrexate	0.1	2.10 ± 0.02
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	25	13.25 ± 3.74
	50	9.50 ± 2.58
	75	6.66 ± 1.70

Mitotic Index Suppression

Analysis of root tip meristems showed a significant decline in mitotic index (MI) with increasing extract concentration. Control samples displayed an MI of $69.60 \pm 5.64\%$, while methotrexate yielded $3.00 \pm 0.68\%$.

Extract-treated groups showed concentration-dependent suppression, with MI values of $15.00 \pm 4.62\%$ (25 mg/mL), $8.20 \pm 2.61\%$ (50 mg/mL), and $5.60 \pm 2.52\%$ (75 mg/mL) (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of different Concentrations of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* extract on cell division and Mitotic index in *A. cepa*.

Treatment group	Concentration of extract (mg/mL)	Total Number of cells	Dividing cells	M.I (%)
Negative control	Tap water	500	348	69.60±5.64
Methotrexate	0.1	500	15	3.00±0.68
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	25	500	75	15.00±4.62
	50	500	41	8.20±2.61
	75	500	28	5.60±2.52

Chromosomal Aberrations

Cytological examination revealed increased chromosomal abnormalities in treated groups relative to the control. Aberrations included stickiness, c-mitosis, vagrant chromosomes, chromosomal breaks, and chromatin bridges. The frequency of aberrant cells rose

with concentration, from 31.32 ± 5.00% at 25 mg/mL to 55.23 ± 5.44% at 75 mg/mL, compared with 2.00 ± 0.28% in the negative control (Table 3, Figure. 3). Physiological aberrations predominated over clastogenic ones.

Table-3: Chromosomal and mitotic aberrations in the root meristematic cells of *Allium cepa* after treatment with *Artocarpus heterophyllus* stem bark extract.

Treatment group	Concentration of extract (mg/mL)	Chromosome breaks (%)±S.E	Stickiness (%) ±S.E	Polar deviation (%)±S.E	Aberrant cells (%)±S.E	MNC (%)± S.E
Negative control	Tap water	-	0.05±0.06	-	2.00±0.28	-
Methotrexate	0.10	2.34±1.23	21.34±5.38	12.20±3.23	45.13±4.22	2.28±0.86
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	25	-	4.25±0.44	-	31.32±5.00	5.12±0.26
	50	-	8.20±3.21	-	36.26±5.67	3.10±2.46
	75	-	9.10±2.10	-	55.23±5.44	-

Values are expressed as mean ±SEM (n=5). Significant at p<0.05 when compared to negative control.

Figure 3: Micrograph showing different stages of mitotic division in cells of *Allium cepa* treated with water extracts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* stem bark. Mag. 40X.

DISCUSSIONS

This study evaluated the cytotoxic and genotoxic potential of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* stem bark extract using the *Allium cepa* assay, a widely recognized model for detecting chromosomal aberrations and mitotic disruption.^[9,11] Our findings demonstrated a concentration-dependent inhibition of root growth, suppression of mitotic index, and induction of chromosomal abnormalities, suggesting that the extract contains bioactive compounds capable of interfering with normal cell division.

The observed root growth inhibition and reduced root number align with previous reports on plant extracts rich in alkaloids, tannins, and phenolics, which often exert antiproliferative effects by disrupting microtubule formation or DNA synthesis.^[12,13] The calculated IC₅₀ of 28 mg/mL indicates moderate cytotoxicity, comparable to other medicinal plants screened via the *Allium cepa* system.

The reduction in mitotic index is a clear indicator of cytostatic activity, reflecting interference with cell cycle progression. Similar decreases have been reported in cells exposed to vincristine and colchicine, classical mitotic poisons.^[14,13] The progressive decline from 15.00% to 5.60% across tested concentrations suggests a dose-related suppression of mitotic activity.

Chromosomal aberrations were predominantly physiological, including c-mitosis, stickiness, and vagrant chromosomes. These abnormalities often arise from spindle poisoning and defective chromatin condensation.^[15] The relatively lower frequency of clastogenic aberrations (e.g., breaks and bridges) suggests that the extract's genotoxicity may be mediated primarily through spindle disruption rather than direct DNA strand breakage.

While *A. heterophyllus* is widely regarded for its nutritional and pharmacological benefits, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties,^[16,17] our findings caution that its stem bark may pose cytogenotoxic risks if used indiscriminately. This duality is not unusual, as many phytochemicals exhibit hormesis — therapeutic at low doses, toxic at higher exposures.^[18]

Limitations of this study include the reliance on a single plant part and assay model. Although the *Allium cepa* test is robust and correlates with mammalian systems, confirmatory studies in mammalian cell lines and in vivo models are needed to establish translational relevance. Future work should also aim to isolate and characterize the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the observed cytotoxicity, alongside pharmacokinetic and safety evaluations.

In conclusion, *A. heterophyllus* stem bark extract exhibits significant cytotoxic and genotoxic activities in the *Allium cepa* assay, underscoring the importance of

cautious use of its bark in traditional medicine. These results highlight the need for rigorous toxicological profiling of medicinal plants, even those with well-established ethnopharmacological reputations.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that methanolic extract of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* stem bark possesses significant cytotoxic and genotoxic activity as evidenced by the *Allium cepa* assay. The extract produced a concentration-dependent inhibition of root growth, suppression of mitotic index, and induction of chromosomal aberrations, predominantly physiological types such as c-mitosis and stickiness. These findings suggest that while *A. heterophyllus* holds considerable ethnomedicinal and pharmacological potential, its stem bark may present safety concerns when used indiscriminately.

Given the global reliance on herbal medicines, this work underscores the importance of toxicological evaluation of medicinal plants to ensure their safe therapeutic use. Further studies should focus on isolating and characterizing the bioactive compounds responsible for the observed effects, validating toxicity in mammalian models, and establishing dose thresholds that balance efficacy with safety.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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